

KINETIC STUDY ON ADSORPTION OF CRUDE OIL FROM OIL-WATER MIXTURE USING A BLEND OF SAWDUST AND JATROPHA OIL-BASED POLYURETHANE FOAM AS ADSORBENT

I. D. Boyede*¹, E. F. Aransiola¹, T. S Oyeniyi¹, J. Sharon¹, A. O. Adetoyese²

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

²Department of Chemical Engineering, Landmark University, Omu-Aran, Nigeria.

*boyedeifeolurwa@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14062805>

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the adsorption of crude oil from oil-water mixtures using jatropa-based polyurethane foam blended with sawdust. The research aims to develop an efficient adsorbent and determined the best isotherm model for the adsorption process. A mesh size of 4.0 mm and weights of 40 g of sawdust were incorporated into the jatropa-based polyurethane foam during production, creating an adsorbent tested across different crude oil-water mixtures (50, 60 and 70 g/L). The adsorption efficiency was analyzed over 15-second intervals. Characterization of the adsorbents was conducted using FTIR and SEM analyses, while the residual oil-water mixture was examined with a UV-spectrophotometer. The experimental data were evaluated against isotherm and kinetic models to ascertain the most suitable model. Results revealed that the lowest density of 0.0164 g/cm³ was achieved. The minimum residual oil concentrations recorded were 5.214, 7,7.142 g/L for sawdust mesh sizes of 4.0 mm and weights of 40 g in the adsorbent for initial oil-water concentrations of 50, 60 and 70g/L respectively. The Langmuir isotherm model provided the best mathematical fit with an R² value of 0.9997, while the pseudo-second-order model was the most suitable for adsorption kinetics with an R² value of 0.9998. The study concluded that a sawdust blend with jatropa-based polyurethane is a potential adsorbent for the adsorption of crude oil from oil-water mixture.

Keywords: Adsorption, Oil Spillage, Adsorbent, Polyurethane Foam, Jatropa curcas oil, Kinetic models

INTRODUCTION

Industrialization has led to environmental pollution due to over-exploitation, inadequate waste management, and improper exploration technology. This pollution inhibits the optimal respiration of living things, causing imbalances and potential diseases. Water pollution is a major challenge, and resolving it permanently is crucial. Crude oil, an essential source of energy and raw material for polymer production, is one of the pollutants of water. The technology used in exploration and transportation poses a danger to the environment, as it poses a threat to the health of living organisms (Adelana *et al.*, 2011).

Oil leakage occurs when liquid petroleum hydrocarbons are released into the environment as a result of human activity and it can lead to ecological degradation. It occurs on land and in water, with water oil spillage occurring when oil is inflow into seas or waterfronts. Crude oil spills have a lower density relative to water, forming floating films or emulsions on (Hoang *et al.*, 2018) water bodies. This can have physical and toxicological impacts on oceanic life, making it inaccessible for residential, water systems, and modern use. If not managed properly, it can lead to the

obliteration of a biological system. Therefore, there is a need to clean up oil spills to ensure environmental safety and the safety of human life (Adelana *et al.*, 2011).

Oil spillage treatment strategies may include gravity, skimming, dispersant application, biodegradation, and sorbent materials. The sorption process is a successful method, using sorbent materials like polypropylene, polyethylene, polyurethane foams, cellulosic materials, and minerals to sorb oil from oil-water blends. Adsorbents can be naturally or synthetically sourced, with synthetic materials like polyethylene and polyurethane being commonly used (Hubbe *et al.*, 2013). Polyurethane is a synthetic material with high porosity, open-cell, low density, and higher oil sorption properties for low-viscosity oils and derivatives (Benjamin *et al.*, 2022; Wu *et al.*, 2014). This method is particularly effective in treating oil spills (Hoang *et al.*, 2018).

The use of natural sorbents like sawdust, sponge gourd, and rice husk is limited due to their non-biodegradability, high cost, and non-renewability (Nwadiogbu *et al.*, 2016). Sawdust, a by-product of woodworking operations, is a renewable, cheap, and biodegradable material with high

Figure 1: FTIR showing Jatropha based Polyurethane with a blend of sawdust before Adsorption (JOPSB)

Figure 2: FTIR showing Jatropha based Polyurethane Foam with Sawdust after Adsorption (JOPSA)

sorption capacity. To improve the biodegradability of the polyurethane foam, the use of jatropha curcas oil was used in replacing the polyol during the production process. This modified polyurethane was further blended with sawdust which gave a higher sorption capacity and improved biodegradability. This is a cheap and environmentally friendly, making it a more suitable alternative for sorption processes (Benjamin *et al.*, 2022).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The reagents used in the production of the blend of sawdust and Jatropha oil based polyurethane adsorbent were all of analytical grades. The sawdust was obtained from sawmills in Ile-Ife. Crude *Jatropha curcas* oil was obtained from the

National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT), Zaria.

The Conversion of Jatropha Curcas oil to Polyol

The raw jatropha curcas oil was converted into polyol by epoxidizing the raw oil and then hydroxylation was done to convert it to polyol (Hoang *et al.*, 2018; Saalah *et al.*, 2017). The jatropha polyol was then used for the production of the adsorbent.

Production of the Adsorbent (A blend of sawdust with Jatropha-based Polyurethane foam)

For the production of a sawdust blend with Jatropha-based polyurethane foam, polyol was added to jatropha oil with a

ratio of 70:30 and then mixed with sawdust (ground sawdust of 4mm mesh size and 40g weight was used) thoroughly for 30 secs. After this, silicon and amine were added to the mixture and the mixing was allowed to continue for 15 seconds. Stannous octoate was then added to the mixture and mixed for another 5 minutes. Lastly, toluene-di-isocyanate (TDI) was added to the mixture and then mixed evenly. The rise and cream time were determined using a stopwatch (Hoang *et al.*, 2018).

Characterization of the Adsorbent Produced

Physical properties of the produced foam tested include density, compression set, indentation hardness and elongation.

Density test

The bulk density (D) of the foam was measured. Two grams of the samples from the adsorbent produced with dimension of 2 cm × 2 cm × 2 cm was cut and weighed on the weighing balance to determine the weight of the adsorbents and mean value of the test-pieces was recorded and the densities determined.

$$\text{Bulk density (D)} = \frac{\text{Mass (M)}}{\text{Volume (V)}} \text{ Kg/m}^3 \quad (1)$$

Compression test

Universal testing machine (Instron-Series 3369) was used to determine the compressibility of the produced foam. Load capacity of 50KN was used for this test. Three test pieces of dimensions 8 cm × 8 cm × 4 cm each was accurately cut and placed in the compression device in turns. The provided spacers and clamps were arranged such that the plates were held parallel to each other and the space between the plates was adjustable to the required height. The test piece was compressed to 75% of its thickness and maintained under room temperature for 22 hours. After 22 hours the piece was removed and placed on wooden materials and allowed to recover for 30 minutes before the thickness T_f was measured. The compression set was then calculated as

$$\text{Compression Set (75\%)} = \frac{T_o - T_f}{T_o} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

T_o = Original thickness

T_f = Final thickness

Indentation hardness test

This test determines the load bearing capacity of the foam. The index is the force required to depress (by 40%) a small circular plate into the foam. To carry out indentation hardness test, the adsorbent (produced foam) sample was placed on the support plate of the test machine. The sample was adjusted so that the center of the sample was located below the center of the indenter. A force of 5 N was applied to the test area and the foam thickness measured. The sample was indented at the rate of 100 mm ± 20 mm per minute to produce an indentation of 70% of the foam

thickness. On reaching 70% indentation, the force was released and the reading taken.

The loading and unloading were repeated twice. Immediately after the 3rd unloading, the sample was indented to 40% of its thickness and maintained in this position for 30 seconds. The corresponding force in Newton was noted as the indentation hardness index.

Cream time and rise time determination

The cream time and rise time of the foam were determined with the aid of a stop clock. The foam chemicals for the foam production were mixed thoroughly and poured inside a prepared mould. The timing started immediately the mixing began. The time elapsed between the mixing of the reactants and the visible start of rising is noted as the cream time.

Fourier transform infrared analysis (FTIR)

The Fourier Transform Infrared (Schimadzu Corporation, Japan) was used to identify the functional group present in jatropha-based polyurethane with a sawdust blend before and after adsorption. Six samples were analysed using FTIR. After the adsorption procedure, the spectrophotometer and spectral values were read and recorded in the 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} range.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphology of jatropha-based polyurethane with a combination of sawdust and jatropha-based polyurethane foam following adsorption was investigated using scanning electron microscopy (VEGA3 TESCAN, Germany). A small amount of the sample was mounted on aluminium stubs using double-sided tape, and the sample was gently coated with carbon to help in accurate surface and cross section visualization while also preventing excessive charging of the sample. All samples were evaluated with an accelerating voltage of 20.0 KV and a magnification of 100x.

Simulation of the Oil-Water Mixture

The oil-water mixture used for the experiment was prepared by contaminating 1L of water with 50, 60 and 70 g of crude oil at normal temperature in a beaker. It was continuously agitated in an incubator shaker for 20 minutes.

Adsorption of the Adsorbate using the Adsorbent Produced

The adsorbent produced was then used for the adsorption process. Two grams of jatropha-based polyurethane with sawdust blend was weighed and carefully dropped on the surface of the contaminated water for 15 seconds. The content of the residual of the oil-water mixture was analysed using a UV-spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 460 nm.

Using Equation 3, the adsorption capacity was calculated.

$$\text{Adsorption capacity} = \left(\frac{c_o}{M} - \frac{c_f}{M} \right) v \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: Surface morphology of the blend of sawdust with JOP (JOPS).

Figure 4: Surface morphology of the blend of sawdust with JOP after adsorption (JOPSA).

Plate 1: Polyurethane before Adsorption

Plate 2: Polyurethane after Adsorption

C_o (mg/L) = Initial concentration,
 C_t (mg/g) = Final concentration after adsorption at any time t ,
 M (g) = Mass of the adsorbent
 V (L) = Volume of the aqueous solution.

To know the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent for both crude oil and water, the residues were weighed and the value was designated as W_2 . Equation 1 was used to calculate and record the adsorption capacity of each treatment type as a function of adsorbent weight as reported by some authors ((Annunciado *et al.*, 2005) (Nwadiogbu *et al.*, 2016).

$$\text{Adsorption capacity, } A.C (\%) = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

W_1 = Initial weight of Adsorbent
 W_2 = Final weight of Adsorbent

The quantity of crude oil remaining in the oil-water combination after the adsorption time was studied to assess the adsorbent's adsorption uptake (jatropha-based polyurethane mixed with sawdust). The UV spectrophotometer analysis was used in their determination.

Effect of Contact Time

The impact of contact time on the adsorption process was examined. A known weight of the adsorbents (2 g) was dropped at different time intervals in the adsorbate. The time was varied from 15-105 seconds using a stopwatch, 15 secs interval was used and adsorbent was removed and the residual oil was measured to determine the corresponding concentration.

Kinetics and Equilibrium Study

To determine the equilibrium concentration of the adsorption process as a function of adsorption time. After production, 2g of the adsorbent was used for adsorption. The adsorbate (oil-water mixture) was prepared using concentrations of 50 g/L, 60 g/L, and 70 g/L. Two grams (2 g) of the adsorbent were immersed in the different concentrations of the adsorbate and timed. The experiment was repeated for all the adsorbents produced. The experimental time was varied from 15-105 seconds with a 15-second interval. The time when the absorbance became constant was 105, the equilibrium time was taken, while the corresponding concentration served as the equilibrium

concentration c_e . The residual oil concentrations, adsorption uptake and percentage oil removal at each time interval were determined using the equation below. The equilibrium adsorption uptake was determined as q_e .

$$q_t = \frac{(c_o - c_f)V}{M} \quad (5)$$

q_t = adsorption uptake of oil (mg/g)

C_f = final concentration after adsorption process (mg/l)

V = Volume of mixture (l)

M = Mass of the adsorbent used (g)

C_o = initial concentration of oil (mg/l)

The % oil removed by the adsorbent was determined by the equation

$$\% \text{ oil removal} = \frac{c_o - c_f}{c_o} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Table 1: Langmuir values for the variables of the oil-water concentration

Langmuir	60g/L	50g/L
Q_m	2821.429	2303.571
R^2	0.8516	0.9994
R_L	0.02016	0.024096
$b=0.00081$		

Table 2: Freundlich values for the variables of the oil-water concentration

Freundlich	60g/L	50g/L
R^2	0.6547	0.9998
K_f	0.7623	0.9951
$N=3.641$		

Table 3: Temkin values for the variables of the oil-water concentration

Temkin	60g/L	50g/L
R^2	0.9435	0.9993
A	12.0151	3.08978
B	2.7342	7.10532

The isotherm and kinetic studies were done using equations of Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm models (Foo & Hameed, 2010; Vijayakumar *et al.*, 2012) and kinetic studies using the Lagergren or pseudo-first-order rate equation (Qiu *et al.*, 2009) and pseudo-second-order model (Nwadiogbu *et al.*, 2016)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The adsorbent with sawdust mixture has large pore sizes and a loosely packed particle with high density as shown in plate Samples of the oil-water mixture before and after adsorption and residual oil collected after the process are shown in Plate 2. A blend of sawdust with jatropha-based polyurethane after adsorption shows oil molecules filling the pores and covering the adsorbent's surface with oils. The study examined the physical properties of a blend of sawdust and jatropha-based polyurethane. The results showed a compressive stress of 0.00363 J, which aligns with the mechanical properties of a good polyurethane form. The density was found to be low at 0.0164 g/cm³, which supports (Hoang *et al.*, 2018) finding that lower density leads to higher adsorption capacity which also supports the finding from (Benjamin *et al.*, 2022)

Characterization of the Adsorbent

FTIR Analyses on before and after adsorption of a sawdust blend with Jatropha-based Polyurethane foam.

The sample was observed both before and after. Major peaks were seen at 2351.39, 1523.00, and 556.00 before adsorption, as indicated in Figure 5. These are the result of the N-O asymmetric stretch in the functional group of nitro compounds, the Br stretch in the functional group of alkyl halides, and the C-N stretch of nitriles. The results match those that were published (Hoang *et al.*, 2018). The following sharp peaks were observed: O-H stretch in the free hydroxyl group, O-H stretch, the H-bonded of the fictitious group, and C-H bend in the functional group, respectively, at 3797.00, 3641.00, 3537.00, and 621.00 cm⁻¹.

After adsorption, alterations were observed and peaks were less prominent and lumped together, as a result of the presence of crude oil in the adsorbent. Sharp peaks were observed at 3303.00 cm⁻¹, 2908.00 cm⁻¹, 2351.00 cm⁻¹ and 416.00 cm⁻¹ as a result of alteration in the O-H stretch in the carbonyl acid functional group, alteration in the C-H in the alkane functional group as shown in Figure 15.

Scanning Electron microscopy (SEM)

Jatropha-based polyurethane foam with a blend of sawdust (JOPS) and jatropha-based polyurethane foam with a blend of sawdust after adsorption (JOPSA) was carried out. The physical morphology of the samples was investigated to observe the porosity. The samples were observed at 26, 50, 100 and 150 magnification and the voltage at 20 KV. It was observed that the porosity of JOPS at 9.24 mm is very many and clear as shown in Figure 17. The semi-major axis ranges from 95.06-258.25 micrometres, the semi-

minor axis is from 61.11-136.60 micrometres. The area ranges from 18248.53-110825.97 micrometre square and the eccentricity ranges from 0.766-0.876. For JOPSA, at 13.44mm width, it was observed that the pores which were

Figure 5: Langmuir Isotherm plot of 70 g/L of the adsorbate

Figure 6: Temkin Isotherm plot of 70 g/L of the adsorbate

Figure 7: Langmuir Isotherm plot of 60 g/L of the adsorbate

Figure 8 Freundlich Isotherm plot of 60 g/L of the adsorbate

open and clear from JOPS are closed. This is due to the presence of the oil that was adsorbed; now filling up the pore spaces as shown in Figure 18. The semi-major axis is 106.37-195.28, the semi-minor axis is from 36.35 -116.64 micrometres, the area ranging from 12147.56-66062.56 micrometres squared and the circumference is 475.76-971.68 micrometres with eccentricity, 0.658-0.940. The analysis shows that the blend of sawdust with the jatrophabased polyurethane foam gives it a very good porosity level. This corresponds with the work done by (Darmadi *et al.*, 2020; Selvasembian *et al.*, 2021).

Effect of Contact Time Equations

The effect of the time of contact between the adsorbent and adsorbate was investigated. The adsorbate concentration was varied from 50 – 70 g/L. The temperature was kept constant at 25 °C, and the weight of the adsorbent used was 2 g. Samples were withdrawn every 15 seconds to determine the residual oil concentration. The highest percentage of oil removal for the concentrations of 50, 60 and 70 g/l were 64.858%, 94.05% and 91.84% respectively. It was observed that for all the concentrations considered there was a rapid

increase in crude oil uptake. The enhanced availability of active sites on the adsorbent surface was the cause of the fast adsorption (Sidik *et al.*, 2012). This is due to the presence of the treated sawdust in the polyurethane. The uptake rate increased progressively and reduced as the time increased to 105 sec. However, the equilibrium was reached after 60 secs but it was left until 105 secs so to ensure that the adsorption process was completed. The steady absorption rate after 60 seconds might be attributed to the saturation of the polyurethane surface with crude oil. The proportion of crude oil eliminated after equilibrium varied across all concentrations.

Adsorption Isotherm study

The experimental data obtained were analysed and used for four different isotherm models of Langmuir, Freundlich, and Temkin isotherms for 50, 60 and 70 g/L respectively as shown in Figure 5-12. The isotherm equations were verified to determine how applicable they are to the adsorption process, using the correlation coefficient R². The Langmuir plot was obtained by plotting C_e/q_e against C_e. Freundlich plot was obtained using ln q_e against ln C_e. For

Table 4: First and second-order parameters

Mode	Parameters	Experiment	q _e (mg/g)	50 g/L	60 g/L
Pseudo- First Order	R ²			0.7635	0.8534
	K ₁ Calculating			0.0808	0.7611
	q ^c (mg/g)			2841.188	2847.96
Pseudo-Second Order	R ²			0.8542	0.9975
	K ₂ (mg/g ^s -1)			6.667E-05	6.250E-05

Figure 13: First order of $\ln(q_e - q_t)$ against time for 50 g/l

Figure 14: Second order of t/q_t against time for 50 g/l

Figure 17: First order of $\ln(q_e - q_t)$ against time for 70 g/l

Figure 18: Second order of t/q_t against time for 70 g/l

the Temkin plot, q_e against $\ln C_e$ was used (Murphy *et al.*, 2023). The values of the isotherm for various grams of the concentration constants and R^2 are given in Table 1-3.

CONCLUSION

The feasibility of producing a blend of sawdust with jatropha-based polyurethane foam was investigated. The effectiveness of the model parameters was studied in the optimization studies. The kinetic and isotherm study was considered. The isotherm models considered in this study show that the Langmuir isotherm model represents the adsorption process very well due to the best mathematical fit obtained from the R^2 value of 0.9997. The dimensionless Langmuir separation factor R_L values obtained for all the

concentrations were less than 1 which implies that favourable adsorption occurred.

It was shown that the duration of adsorption affected the adsorption process. As soon as the adsorbent was introduced to the oil-water combination, a quick rate of crude oil absorption was seen. This rate increased, albeit slowly, until equilibrium was established. The best mathematical fit to the experimental results, as indicated by the R^2 values of 0.9998, 0.9749 and 0.9992 for the concentrations of 50,60 and 70 g/L, respectively, indicates that the pseudo-second-order model best explains the observed rate and adsorption kinetics. The agreement of the model with the experimental data was also confirmed by a chi-square statistical test which was performed on the

experimentally determined values and the values calculated from the models. Hence, the addition of sawdust in the jatropha-based polyurethane gave a better adsorbent for the removal of crude oil from water more effective.

REFERENCES

- Adelana, S. O., Adeosun, T. A., Adesina, A. O., & Ojuoye, M. O. (2011). Environmental pollution and remediation: Challenges and management of oil Spillage in the Nigerian coastal areas. *American Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research*, 2(6), 834–845. <https://www.scribbr.com/AJSIR/PDF/2011/6/AJSIR-2-6-834-845.pdf>
- Annunciado, T. R., Sydenstricker, T. H. D., & Amico, S. C. (2005). Experimental investigation of various vegetable fibers as sorbent materials for oil spills. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 50(11), 1340–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2005.04.043>
- Benjamin, T. J., Yu, L. J., Thomas Raymond, D. A., & Lai, N. Y. G. (2022). Preparation and Water Absorption Analysis of Polyurethane Foam Reinforced Sawdust Composites. In A. S. Abdul Sani, M. N. Osman Zahid, M. R. Mohamad Yasin, S. Z. Ismail, M. Z. Mohd Zawawi, A. R. Abdul Manaf, S. N. Mohd Saffe, R. Abd Aziz, & F. Mohd Turan (Eds.), *Enabling Industry 4.0 through Advances in Manufacturing and Materials* (pp. 317–326). Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-2890-1_31
- Darmadi, Lubis, M. R., Saputra, R., Alfarabi, M. D., Sarah, S., & Adisalamun. (2020). Characterization of Modified Polyurethane Foam Adsorbents for Mercury Adsorption Applications. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 845(1), 012002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/845/1/012002>
- Foo, K. Y., & Hameed, B. H. (2010). Insights into the modeling of adsorption isotherm systems. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 156(1), 2–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2009.09.013>
- Hoang, A. T., Le, V. V., Al-Tawaha, A. R. M. S., Nguyen, D. N., Al-Tawaha, A. R. M. S., Noor, M. M., & Pham, V. V. (2018). An adsorption capacity investigation of new adsorbent based on polyurethane foams and rice straw for oil spill cleanup. *Petroleum Science and Technology*, 36(5), 361–370. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10916466.2018.1425722>
- Murphy, O. P., Vashishtha, M., Palanisamy, P., & Kumar, K. V. (2023). A Review on the Adsorption Isotherms and Design Calculations for the Optimization of Adsorbent Mass and Contact Time. *ACS Omega*, 8(20), 17407–17430. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.2c08155>
- Nwadiogbu, J. O., Ajiwe, V. I. E., & Okoye, P. A. C. (2016). Removal of crude oil from aqueous medium by sorption on hydrophobic corncobs: Equilibrium and kinetic studies. *Journal of Taibah University for Science*, 10(1), 56–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtusci.2015.03.014>
- Saalah, S., Abdullah, L. C., Aung, M. M., Salleh, M. Z., Awang Biak, D. R., Basri, M., Jusoh, E. R., & Mamat, S. (2017). Physicochemical Properties of Jatropha Oil-Based Polyol Produced by a Two Steps Method. *Molecules*, 22(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22040551>
- Selvasembian, R., Gwenzi, W., Chaukura, N., & Mthembu, S. (2021). Recent advances in the polyurethane-based adsorbents for the decontamination of hazardous wastewater pollutants. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 417, 125960. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.125960>
- Shittu, T., Aransiola, E., & Alabi-Babalola, O. (2020). Adsorption Performance of Modified Sponge Gourd for Crude Oil Removal. *Journal of Environmental Protection*, 11, 65–81. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jep.2020.112006>
- Sidik, S. M., Jalil, A. A., Triwahyono, S., Adam, S. H., Satar, M. A. H., & Hameed, B. H. (2012). Modified oil palm leaves adsorbent with enhanced hydrophobicity for crude oil removal. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 203, 9–18. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1385894712008625>
- Vijayakumar, G., Senthilnathan, P., Pandurangan, K., & Ramakrishna, G. (2012). IMPACT AND ENERGY ABSORPTION CHARACTERISTICS OF LATHE SCRAP REINFORCED CONCRETE.
- Wu, G., Chen, J., Huo, S., Liu, G., & Kong, Z. (2014). Thermoset nanocomposites from two-component waterborne polyurethanes and cellulose whiskers. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 105, 207–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2014.01.095>